

Identification of Another 4Q87 (4QPs-e) Fragment (Ps 87:4-6 with a textual variant): PAM 43.678 frag. 8 / IAA Plate 78 frag. 9

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One of the many hitherto unidentified small fragments from Qumran Cave 4 should be identified as a fragment of 4Q87 (4QPs^e), published in DJD 16. The fragment is included on IAA Plate 78, one of the forty or so museum plates with Cave 4 fragments that had not yet been identified by 1959. This plate was photographed as PAM 43.678 (<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285457>) and included in DJD 33. In this photo the fragment is at the top left of the plate, and in the edition it was numbered frag. 8. Subsequently some fragment have been removed from this plate and some others rearranged. Presently the fragment is in the top second row, the second fragment from the left (for an overview of the plate in 2014 see: <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-497952>). The fragment itself was photographed in 2014 in colour (<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-492594>) and in infrared (<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-492595>), but the top of the fragment has suffered in between 1959 and 2014, and its traces are better legible on the 1959 photograph (left image) than on the 2014 one (right image).

The DJD editors transcribed part of the fragment correctly, but failed to offer an identification. The textual remains (8 complete letters and 7 damaged ones) correspond within the Hebrew Bible exclusively with Ps 87:4-6, whereas palaeographically the script matches with that of 4Q87. One may note that the remains of 4Q87 range from Psalms 76 to Ps 130, and that 4Q87 frag. 4 is a remnant of Ps 86:10-11 and frag. 5 of Ps 88:1-5.

One may read the fragment as following, with the lost text of Ps 87:4-6 provided in square brackets:

[עיר האלהים סלה⁴ אזכיר רהב¹] בבל ליד² [עי הנה פלשת] 1
[וצור עם כוש זה ילד שם⁵ ולציון] יאמר א³ [יש ואיש ילד בה] 2
[והוא יכוננה עליון⁶ יהוה יספר] בכתב³ [עמים זה ילד שם] 3

Typical of the hand of 4Q87 is its frequent shading. The scribe drew broad horizontal strokes, but thinner (sometimes extremely thin) downstrokes. The same feature is found in the IAA Plate 78 fragment. See, e.g., the *resh* of יאמר, or the (only partially preserved) *taw* in line 3. Other shared features between 4Q87 and the Plate 78 fragment are: hook-like keraiai at the right arm of *alef*; the

thick, long, triangular head of *yod*; the thickening of the top of the upperarm of *lamed*; the downstroke of medial *mem* slopes down, and its arm joins to the the downstroke of the next letter.

As in some other 4Q87 fragments (e.g., frag. 5) the leather has become brittle.

What does this small fragment add to our knowledge? Orthographically, 4Q87 tends to use *waw* for /o/ and /u/. However, according to the remains of line 3, the fragment had here בכתב as against the MT בכתוב, “as he registers.” Rather than presenting a defective spelling of the MT reading, it is more likely that the fragment reflects the reading בכתב, “in a list,” as is also indicated in the LXX κύριος διηγῆσεται ἐν γραφῇ λαῶν (LXX Ps 86:6).

MT Ps 87:6	LXX Ps 86:6
<p style="text-align: center;">יְהוָה יִסְפֹּר בְּכִתּוּב עַמִּים זֶה יֵלֵד-שָׁם סֵלָה:</p>	<p>κύριος διηγῆσεται ἐν γραφῇ λαῶν καὶ ἀρχόντων τούτων τῶν γεγενημένων ἐν αὐτῇ. διάψαλμα.</p>
<p>The LORD records <i>as he registers</i> the peoples, “This one was born there.” <i>Selah</i> (NRSV)</p>	<p>The Lord will recount, <i>in a list of</i> peoples, and rulers, those that were born in it. <i>Interlude on strings</i> (NETS)</p>

References and Abbreviations

DJD 16	Eugene Ulrich and others, <i>Qumran Cave 4 XI Psalms to Chronicles</i> , Discoveries in the Judaean Desert XVI (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2000)
DJD 33	Dana M. Pike and Andrew C. Skinner, <i>Qumran Cave 4 XXIII Unidentified Fragments</i> , Discoveries in the Judaean Desert XXXIII (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2001)
IAA	Israel Antiquities Authority
LXX	Septuagint
MT	Masoretic Text
NETS	New English Translation of the Septuagint
NRSV	New Revised Standard Version
PAM	Palestine Archaeological Museum

Images

Images as screenshots from

left: <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285457>

right: <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-492595>